

**The International Journal of Network Security & Its Applications
(IJNSA)**

(ERA, UGC Listed Journal)

ISSN 0974 - 9330 (Online); 0975 - 2307 (Print)

<http://airccse.org/journal/ijnsa.html>

November 2018, Volume 10, Number 6

A Multi-Layer Hybrid Text Steganography for Secret Communication Using Word Tagging and RGB Color Coding

Ali F. Al-Azzawi1, Philadelphia University, Jordan

Secure Third Party Auditor(TPA) for Ensuring Data Integrity in Fog Computing

KashifMunir and Lawan A. Mohammed, University of Hafr Al Batin, KSA

IOT and Security-Privacy Concerns: A Systematic Mapping Study

Moussa WITTI and Dimitri KONSTANTAS, Information Science Institute University of Geneva, Switzerland

Biometric Smartcard Authentication for Fog Computing

Kashif Munir and Lawan A. Mohammed, University of Hafr Al Batin, KSA

http://airccse.org/journal/jnsa18_current.html